

STUDIES ON REACTIONS OF SULPHONAZIDES WITH PYRIDINE.

PART I. SALTS AND DERIVATIVES OF PYRIDINE-IMINE

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p-Acetylaminobenzene sulphonazide and *p*-toluene sulphonazide were respectively heated with excess of pyridine. The main reaction products were proved respectively to be *p*-acetylaminobenzene sulphon-*N*-iminopyridine and *p*-toluene sulphon-*N*-iminopyridine. These substances were hydrolysed and different salts and derivatives of *N*-iminopyridine were prepared. The free base *N*-iminopyridine was also liberated, but found to be quite unstable. The *N*-iminopyridine structure has finally been confirmed by *total* synthesis.

In course of studies on the reaction of sulphonazides, Curtius and Kraemers (*J. prakt. Chem.*, 1930, 125, 323) heated *p*-toluene sulphonazides with pyridine and isolated a crystalline compound ($C_{12}H_{11}O_2N_2S$, m. p. 210°). They supposed it to be *p*-toluene sulphonamidopyridine. The base, remaining after removal of *p*-toluene sulphonic acid by hydrolysis, formed a picrate, m. p. 138-39°. But this melting point of the picrate did not agree with the m. p. of any of the picrates of known aminopyridines. Though they called this base an aminopyridine, they were not definite about its exact structure. Moreover, the reactions of this compound, as described by them, are quite different from those expected from the three known aminopyridines.

In the present communication, the detailed study of the action of different sulphonazides on pyridine is described.

In the first instance, *p*-acetylaminobenzene sulphonazide (Curtius, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1926, 112, 128) has been heated at about 150° for 30 hours with five times its weight of pyridine in a CO_2 atmosphere and the evolved gas collected. The gas is found to be nitrogen and forms 92% of the amount required by the equation :

During the course of reaction yellowish white crystalline incrustation is formed. After repeated crystallisations, the substance melts with decomposition at 284°, the yield being very small.

From the reaction mixture a number of different substances has also been isolated. Their structure and properties will be published in subsequent communications.

The reaction does not take place at lower temperature. Even at 100°, no nitrogen is found to evolve and the azide is recovered unchanged after distillation of pyridine in vacuum. Moreover, the reaction cannot be completed in a shorter time as some unchanged azide is found to remain even after heating at 150° for 11 hours. Reduction of the quantity of pyridine to twice the amount of the azide also leads to an explosion of the azide.

Estimation of C, H, N and S of the substance of m. p. 284° shows that it has the empirical formula $C_{12}H_{11}O_2N_2S$. This is insoluble in pyridine, alcoholic and aqueous

caustic solutions, even at a slightly elevated temperature. Diazo reaction for primary amino group is found negative at first, but on mild hydrolysis with dilute hydrochloric acid, the diazo reaction is positive.

The hydrolysed product is beautifully crystalline, m. p. 228.5°. Estimations of C, H, N and molecular weight show that it has the formula $C_{11}H_{11}O_2N_2S$, of which one of the nitrogen forms the part of an aromatic primary amino group. Hence the formula can be written as $NH_2\{C_{11}H_9O_2N_2S\}$

Estimation of Pt in the platinum chloride derivative (m. p. 224°) indicates the formula $\{C_{11}H_{11}O_2N_2S\}_2PtCl_6$ showing that it has two basic groups. Evidently the amino group is one of the basic groups, while the other must be contained in the $(C_{11}H_9O_2N_2S)$ -residue.

The substance of m. p. 228.5° can be further hydrolysed by heating with concentrated hydrochloric acid to sulphanilic acid and hydrochloride of a base. The latter can be easily converted into a perchlorate (m. p. 204°). Analytical data and molecular weight determination indicate its formula as $C_5H_6N_2.HClO_4$.

Hence the formula $C_{11}H_{11}O_2N_2S$ may be expanded to $NH_2.C_6H_4.SO_2\{C_5H_5N_2\}$ which by the addition of a molecule of water, during hydrolysis, produces $NH_2.C_6H_4.SO_3H$ and $C_5H_6N_2$. The base $C_5H_6N_2$ is extremely unstable in the free state, but quite stable as salts and derivatives.

By the action of nitrous acid on the perchlorate of the base in the cold, nitrogen is evolved and pyridine is obtained in the solution which is identified as pyridine perchlorate. So the base may be represented as (I) which contains a pyridine nucleus.

Alkaline ferricyanide is also found to liberate half the amount of nitrogen from the perchlorate of the base. The base is quite different from any of the three aminopyridines. Now, if the additional nitrogen be attached to any two carbon atoms of the pyridine ring, then a cyclic polymethylene-imine ring would result. But this type of ring systems is quite stable to oxidising agents and no evolution of nitrogen occurs (Howard and Marckwald, *Ber.*, 1899, 32, 2036). Moreover, there would result a di-acidic base, but this compound is a mono-acidic base, as is evident from the analytical data of its picrate, perchlorate and platinichloride. The additional nitrogen atom may be attached directly to the nitrogen atom of the pyridine ring. Then the base must have the structure (II) (III), (IV), or (V).

By exhaustive hydrogenation of the base-hydrochloride with palladium-charcoal catalyst in alcoholic suspension, piperidine is obtained, and identified as its perchlorate. In course of this hydrogenation 8 atoms of hydrogen per molecule are taken up.

By partial hydrogenation of the compound $C_{11}H_{11}O_2N_2S$ (m. p. 228.5°) by palladium-charcoal in acetic acid suspension, acetylsulphanilamide and pyridine are obtained and identified. During this course, 2 atoms of hydrogen are allowed to be taken up. These findings can only be explained if the base have structure (V); otherwise in structures (II), (III), or (IV), only 4 atoms of hydrogen per molecule can be taken up in the exhaustive hydrogenation and the product of hydrogenation would have been quite different. Hence the structure of the compound $C_{12}H_{12}O_2N_2S$ must be represented by (VI).

From the consideration of the adjustment of electrons in the compound (VI), it is evident that the nature of the linkage between the two nitrogen is of the semipolar-double-bond type, in which case the ring nitrogen (VII) acts as a donor

and the extra nitrogen as an acceptor. This is also quite in agreement with the mono-acid character of the base.

Similar type of linkage was also predicted to exist between nitrogen and oxygen in the case of pyridine-N-oxide and quinoline-N-oxide (Meisenheimer, *Ber.*, 1926, 59, 1848). Schneider also reported a few compounds obtained by the action of phenylhydrazine on substituted pyryllium salts (*Annalen*, 1924, 439, 115; *cf. Chem. Rev.*, 1944, 35, 92). His coloured anhydro-bases were supposed to have a grouping $\equiv \text{N} = \text{N} -$, which he accounted for the production of colour.

The work of Curtius and Kraemers (*loc. cit.*) with *p*-toluene sulphonazide and pyridine has been repeated in absence of air. The reaction product after crystallisation from alcohol has a m. p. 210° as mentioned by the original authors. The base-hydrochloride obtained by hydrolysis of this compound (m. p. 210°) is found

to be identical with the base-hydrochloride obtained from *p*-acetylaminobenzene sulphonimidopyridine compound. Other derivatives of the base viz., perchlorate, picrate and platinichloride are also found to be identical with those of the previous one. This has further been confirmed by allowing *p*-acetylaminobenzene sulphochloride to react on this base (from the *p*-toluene compound) which leads to the production of compound (VI). Hence the Curtius-Kraemer compound of m. p. 210° must have the structure (VIII).

The N-iminopyridine structure has further been confirmed by the direct synthesis of the compound (VIII.)

Monobenzoyl derivative of glutaconic dialdehyde (IX) is obtained from pyridine (Baumgarten, *Ber.*, 1924, B, 57, 1625) and condensed with *p*-toluene sulphonylhydrazide. The compound (X) suffers ring-closure with the elimination of ethyl benzoate. The substance obtained after neutralisation is found identical with the compound (VIII) obtained by Curtius process.

Further investigations about this interesting class of compounds are in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL

Reaction of p-Acetylaminobenzene sulphonazide with Pyridine.—Pure and dry *p*-acetylaminobenzene sulphonazide (30 g.) was heated under reflux with freshly distilled pyridine (150 g.) at 150° in a metal-bath. The apparatus was connected to a nitrometer, filled with 50% caustic potash and the air in the system was replaced by a slow stream of dry carbon dioxide. Heating was continued in the CO₂-atmosphere for 30 hours until no more nitrogen evolved. Total nitrogen evolved was 2914 c.c. at 30°/760.2 mm. A hard, crystalline, yellowish white incrustation was formed inside the vessel. This was separated from the main reaction mixture by filtration. The substance is sparingly soluble in alcohol and water, more soluble in acetic acid and also in dilute hydrochloric acid. It was repeatedly crystallised from alcohol and finally crystallised from dilute acetic acid and obtained as yellowish white, highly refracting prismatic crystals, m.p. 284° (decomp.), yield 5.2 g. (This is referred in this paper as compound A).

(Found : C, 53.62 ; H, 4.14 ; N, 14.18 ; S, 10.61. $C_{13}H_{13}O_2N_2S$ requires C, 53.6 ; H, 4.47 ; N, 14.43 ; S, 11.0 per cent).

The dark brown mother-liquor after separation of the compound (A) was distilled in vacuum and from the tarry residue a number of different substances was obtained.

Deacetylation of Compound (A).—Compound (A) (2.9 g.) was suspended in alcohol and the mixture was saturated with hydrochloric acid gas in cold, when most of the suspensions went into solution. The solution was allowed to stand in a refrigerator for 24 hours when large, cubic, hygroscopic crystals separated out which were collected. The filtrate, which strongly smelled of ethyl acetate and hydrochloric acid was concentrated in vacuum and a further crop of crystals was obtained. The crystals were collected, dissolved in water and just neutralised with sodium carbonate, when the amino compound (compound B) precipitated. The substance was crystallised from absolute alcohol (charcoal) as fine, light yellow crystals, m. p. 228.5°, yield 2.3 g. It is insoluble in water. (Found : N, 16.54. $C_{11}H_{11}O_2N_2S$ requires N, 16.86 per cent).

The substance can be diazotised and coupled with alkaline β -naphthol with the production of beautiful red colour.

Platinichloride derivative of compound (B) was prepared in the usual way and after crystallisation from dilute hydrochloric acid (0.1N) melted at 224°. (Found : Pt, 30.01. $C_{11}H_{11}O_2N_2S, H_2PtCl_4$ requires Pt, 29.65 per cent).

Complete Hydrolysis of compound (B).—The substance (2.4 g.) was heated with concentrated hydrochloric acid (30 c. c.) for 5 hours under reflux. The resulting solution was concentrated under vacuum to about 10 c.c. and then cooled to 0°. The crystals were filtered off and washed with ice-water. The filtrate and washings were again concentrated in vacuum to about 3 c.c., cooled and the crystals were filtered off, yield 1.61 g. It proved to be sulphanilic acid by the usual tests and also by converting it into 1:3:5-tribromoaniline, m. p. 119°.

The filtrate was decolourised by animal charcoal and concentrated in vacuum. The hydrochloride of a base (compound C) was obtained as colourless, long crystals. It is extremely hygroscopic and also highly soluble in methyl and ethyl alcohol. It gives a violet coloration with alkali, and a red coloration with alkaline nitroprusside.

Perchlorate of compound (C) was obtained from an alcoholic solution of the hydrochloride of compound (C) (0.2 g.) and perchloric acid solution (1 c. c., 70%) as fine white crystals. It crystallised from absolute alcohol, m. p. 204°, yield 0.17 g. It gives a violet coloration with alkali and a red coloration with alkaline nitroprusside. [Found: N, 14.14 ; M. W. (by freezing point method in water), 190. $C_5H_5N_2, HClO_4$ requires N, 14.39 per cent. M. W., 194.5).

Picrate of Compound (C).—A methyl alcoholic solution of the hydrochloride of compound (C) (0.5 g.) was added to a suspension of freshly prepared silver oxide (1 g.) in methyl alcohol in cold. The mixture was rapidly shaken and immediately filtered. The filtrate was immediately added to a saturated solution of picric acid in

methyl alcohol (5 c. c.) in cold. After a few hours' standing in cold, the picrate was filtered off, and washed with a little cold methyl alcohol. It crystallised from methyl alcohol as orange plates, m. p. 149°. (Found: N, 21.92. $C_{11}H_6O_2N$, requires N, 21.66 per cent).

By keeping a bit longer in presence of silver oxide, silver oxide was reduced to silver even in cold and the solution became deep violet in colour. From this solution no picrate could be obtained.

Platinichloride of compound (C) crystallised from dilute hydrochloric acid (0.1N) as long, golden yellow plates, m. p. 237° (decomp.). [Found: Pt, 32.93. $(C_5H_6N_2)_2H_2PtCl_6$ requires Pt, 32.62 per cent].

Action of Nitrous acid on Perchlorate of Compound (C).—The perchlorate (0.2 g.) was dissolved in water (5 c. c.) and to this perchloric acid (70% 0.5 c. c.) was added. Then a solution of potassium nitrite (0.1 g. in 2 c. c.) was added in cold and left for 12 hours. The solution was evaporated in vacuum and treated with alcohol. The potassium perchlorate was filtered off and from the filtrate a perchlorate was obtained, m. p. 282° (mixed m. p. with pyridine perchlorate).

Action of Alkaline Ferricyanide on Perchlorate of Compound (C).—Aqueous solution of the perchlorate (0.201 g. in 20 c. c. water) was taken in a three-necked flask (100 c. c.), the necks of which were respectively connected to (i) a CO_2 -Kipp's apparatus, (ii) a dropping funnel with drawn end and (iii) a nitrometer, filled with 50% KOH solution. The air in the flask was completely chased out by a slow stream of CO_2 . Then an alkaline solution of potassium ferricyanide was slowly introduced into the flask and it was slightly warmed on a water-bath. The gas measured 12.70 c. c. at 29.5°/759.5 mm.

A parallel blank experiment was also performed and the gas evolved was negligible (0.05 c. c. at 29.5°/759.5 mm.).

Liberation of Compound (C) from its Perchlorate.—The perchlorate (0.4141 g.) was dissolved in absolute alcohol (30 c. c., free from aldehyde) and cooled in a freezing mixture. Then freshly prepared alcoholic potash (15 c. c. of 0.1355N; 15.97 c. c. actually required) was added slowly. The mixture was kept at 0° for 12 hours and rapidly filtered in cold. The solution was violet in colour and had a strong basic odour. The alcohol was distilled off at low temperature in vacuum. A deep violet scaly substance with a strong basic odour was obtained. It is soluble in water, benzene, alcohol, ether and chloroform. The violet colour of the solution is discharged on acidification. The substance rapidly transformed into a black resinous matter at room temperature, even in vacuum or in solution, and the solubility as well as other properties were lost after this transformation.

Catalytic Hydrogenation of Hydrochloride of Compound (C).—A solution of the hydrochloride (0.201 g.) in ethyl alcohol (20 c. c.) and fused sodium acetate (0.15 g.) were shaken with 0.2 g. of 10% palladium-charcoal catalyst (which had been previously saturated with hydrogen) in an atmosphere of hydrogen. 155 C. c. of hydrogen at 30°/759 mm. were absorbed within 3 hours. $(C_5H_6N_2)$ requires 153.3 c. c. at 30°/759 mm.)

The solution was filtered and the solvent concentrated in vacuum. Perchloric acid solution (5 drops) was added, the solution cooled and the crystals filtered off and recrystallised as fine white crystals, m. p. 129° (mixed m. p. with piperidine perchlorate).

Catalytic Hydrogenation of Compound (B).—A solution of compound (B) (0.25 g.) in glacial acetic acid (25 c. c.) was shaken with 0.2 g. of 10% palladium-charcoal catalyst (which had been previously saturated with hydrogen) in an atmosphere of hydrogen. The shaking was stopped when 25 c. c. of hydrogen at 30°/759 mm. had been absorbed ($C_{11}H_{11}O_2N_2S$ requires 24.8 c. c. of hydrogen at 30°/759 mm.). The solution was filtered off, and the solvent removed in vacuum. The residue was treated with water (10 c. c.) and the crystals filtered off. After crystallisation from water, the substance was obtained as fine, white needles, m. p. 219° (mixed m. p. with *N*⁴-acetyl-sulphanilamide).

The filtrate was acidified with a few drops of perchloric acid, concentrated in vacuum and treated with alcohol. A white perchlorate was obtained which after crystallisation had a m. p. 282° (mixed m. p. with pyridine perchlorate).

Repetition of Curtius-Kraemers Reaction.—*p*-Toluene sulphonazide (20 g.) was heated with pyridine (150 c. c.) in absence of moisture and air, in a CO_2 atmosphere. The heating was continued for 30 hours at 130°. The solid reaction product was filtered off and was obtained as fine, white crystals (compound D), m. p. 210°, yield 7.9 g. (same as mentioned by original authors).

The substance (5 g.) was hydrolysed by heating with concentrated hydrochloric acid (30 c. c.) in a sealed tube for 12 hours at 135°. The crystals were filtered and proved to be *p*-toluene sulphonic acid. The filtrate was decolorised by animal charcoal, filtered, and evaporated in vacuum. The hydrochloride (compound E) was obtained as extremely hygroscopic long plates. It gave a violet coloration with alkali and a red coloration with alkaline nitroprusside.

The perchlorate was obtained from the hydrochloride (compound E), and had a m. p. 204° (mixed m. p. with perchlorate from compound C).

The platinichloride melted at 237° (mixed m. p. with the platinichloride of compound C).

The picrate melted at 149° (mixed m. p. with the picrate of compound C).

Reaction of Compound (E) with p-Acetylamino benzene sulphochloride.—To an aqueous solution of 0.26 g. of the hydrochloride (compound E), cooled to 0°, was added slowly and simultaneously *p*-acetylamino benzene sulphochloride (0.4 g.) and 10% sodium hydroxide solution (1.6 c. c.) with rapid and constant stirring. After 1 hour, the white precipitate was filtered off, washed with cold water and alcohol. After crystallisation from alcohol and acetic acid, the substance was obtained as prismatic crystals, m. p. 284° (decomp.), mixed m. p. with *p*-acetylamino benzene sulphonimido-pyridine (compound A, m. p. 284°, decomp.).

Total Synthesis of Compound (D), (VIII).—Monobenzoyl derivative of glutamic dialdehyde (IX), prepared from pyridine (Baumgarten, *loc. cit.*) was dissolved in dry ether and to this solution was added an ethereal solution of *p*-toluene sulphonylhydra-

side (1.9 g. Curtius, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1930, 125, 323) and left in cold for 3 days. Light yellow crystals began to separate, which were filtered off. A further crop of crystals was obtained on removal of the ether. The crystals were collected and recrystallised from methyl alcohol as light yellow scales, yield 2.1 g. (Found: N, 7.96. $C_{11}H_{11}O_4N_2S$ requires N, 8.22 per cent).

The hydrazone (1 g.) was dissolved in absolute alcohol (20 c. c.) and to this was added 2 c. c. of alcoholic hydrochloric acid (saturated at 25°). The solution was warmed at 45° for 3 hours, when smell of ethyl benzoate was obtained. The solution was concentrated in vacuum and ether (10 c. c.) was added. The crystals were filtered off, washed with ether and dissolved in minimum amount of water. The solution was neutralised with potassium carbonate and the precipitate was filtered off and washed with water. After crystallisation from alcohol the substance had a m. p. 310° (mixed m. p. with Curtius Kraemer's compound obtained from *p*-toluene sulphonazide)

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